

Brain Tumor Classification by Using Extracted Deep CNN Features with Multiple Base Classifiers

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Abstract: The classification of brain tumor is a significant issue in computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) for medical applications. This study focuses on a three-class classification issue to distinguish between three common forms of brain cancers: glioma, meningioma, and pituitary tumors. To extract feature from brain MRI images, the proposed classification method employs deep transfer learning and a pre-trained Google Net. To categorize the extracted features, proven classifier models are used. The purposed system outperforms all current approaches with a mean classification accuracy. The precision, recall, F-score, and specificity are some of the other performance indicators employed in the study. Transfer learning appears to be a helpful strategy when the availability of medical pictures is restricted, in the observation of the previous study. Used NCA to select important feature which help in time consumption during experiments.

Keywords: machine learning; brain tumor classification; k-nearest neighbors; transfer learning; support vector machine

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Introduction

Brain tumors require an accurate and timely diagnosis in order to establish an effective treatment plan. The treatment technique chosen is determined on the tumor's stage at the time of diagnosis, pathological kind, and grade. In a variety of ways, computer-aided diagnostic (CAD) approaches have benefited neuro-oncologists. Tumor detection, classification, and grading are all CAD applications in neuro-oncology. The classification of benign and malignant brain tumors using CAD is a well-studied issue [1]. Another research problem in this domain is grading glioma, which is a prominent class of malignant tumors [2]. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) pictures of the brain are used in the aforementioned CAD systems. This is due to the fact that MRI pictures have a stronger contrast for soft tissues in the brain than computed tomography (CT) pictures.

Because of the emergence of deep learning concepts, recent work on computer-aided medical diagnosis has improved performance. In the medical image analysis of breast cancer research [3] and lung cancer detection [4, deep learning

algorithms have been widely applied. In dermatological diagnostics, author created a deep learning method for human skin identification. [5] To monitor brain metastases, authors employed a deep convolutional neural network (CNN). [6] Deep transfer learning, a subclass of deep learning, has recently dominated research on visual categorization, object recognition, and image classification challenges [7].

Transfer learning allows you to employ a pre-trained CNN model that was originally created for another related purpose. Transfer learning has also been demonstrated to be useful in the diagnosis of medical problems. On CT scans, author employed a pre-trained InceptionV3 model to distinguish between benign and malignant kidney cancers. [8] On histopathologic image, authors suggested a classifier for breast cancer. [9] The authors extracted features using a pre-trained VGG-16 model and a fine-tuned AlexNet, which were then classified by using a support vector machine (SVM). [10] Introducing a learning approach for identifying lung tumors and identifying pancreatic tumors. The learning model used a 3D CNN architecture and was based on knowledge transfer. The accuracy metrics acquired using transfer learning-based algorithms were better than those achieved via handcrafted engineering.

Transfer learning, in particular, has gotten a lot of interest in the field of neuro-oncology. Pretrained networks were used in studies to extract deep features from brain MRI images [11, 12]. The research demonstrated transfer learning's capacity to work with smaller datasets. In their study of glioma grading using MRI scans, authors employed AlexNet and Google Net. In terms of the observed performance metrics, Google Net outperformed AlexNet for the challenge. [13] In their work on brain abnormality classification, authors used deep transfer learning to obtain exceptional classification results. The tests comprised training of modified dense layers, training with data augmentation, and fine tuning of a transfer learned model using ResNet-34. The results of the experiments showed that a deep transfer learning model may be used to classify medical images with minimal pre-processing.[14] For Alzheimer's disease diagnosis via MRI, authors employed a pre-trained VGG-16 network.[15]

For brain tumors, transfer learning was used in content-based image retrieval (CBIR) [16]. The valuable results were recorded while performing evaluation on a publicly available dataset. The classification of brain tumors into subtypes is a more difficult scientific topic. The following reasons are to blame for the associated difficulties: 1) brain tumors vary greatly in shape, size, and severity [17], and 2) tumors of various pathogenic categories can have similar appearances [18]. Glioma, meningioma, and pituitary tumor have the highest incidence rates of all brain tumors [16]. The scientists used a variety of image feature and a number of classifier models in their research. An SVM model based on bag of words (Bow) characteristics produced the best classification results. A typical five-fold cross-validation approach was used in the studies. Specificity, sensitivity, and classification accuracy were the performance metrics employed. Ismael and Abdel-Qatar [19] suggested a classification technique based on statistical characteristics retrieved using a Gabor filter and a discrete wavelet transform (DWT). A multi-layer perceptron (MLP) classifier was then trained using the features. The technique was tested on the figshare dataset, which has been utilized in prior research [17]. The training set and validation set were created by randomly dividing the database photos into 70 percent and 30 percent, respectively.

The considered brain tumor classification problem was successfully solved using a CNN-based deep learning model [20]. CNN-based classifier systems have the benefit of eliminating the need for manually segmented tumor areas and providing a completely automated classifier. In their study, authors used a CNN architecture for feature extraction purpose from brain MRI. [21] The model included five learnable layers with 3x3 filter sizes across all of them. The classification accuracy of the CNN model was 81 percent. The recall measures for the class pituitary tumor were quite high in this study, whereas those for meningioma were quite low. This indicates that the classifier's discriminating capacity is limited. Authors utilized a modified CNN architecture known as a capsule network (CapsNet) to classify brain tumors. [22] The spatial link between the tumor and its surrounding tissues was used by CapsNet. Even yet, there was only a little boost in performance.

The following are the limits of existing works on the classification of brain cancers into meningioma, glioma, and pituitary tumors. Given the medical importance of the classification problem, the performance of state-of-the-art algorithms is insufficient. Prior to classification, earlier approaches depended on manually drawn tumor sections. They were unable to be fully automated as a result of this. Automatic algorithms based on CNN and its derivatives were unable to make a significant improvement in performance. Furthermore, the current approaches were tried on the imbalanced figshare dataset (with respect to tumor classes). As a result, evaluating performance using criteria other than accuracy is important. Another reality is that no research has been done to address the issue of data scarcity that might arise in practice.

We provide an accurate and automated classification approach for three forms of brain tumors (glioma, meningioma, and pituitary tumor) in this paper. To extract features from brain MRI images, the solution use a deep transfer learning CNN model, Known classifiers are used to classify the extracted feature. The proposed system is next subjected to a rigorous assessment.

When tested on the available dataset from figshare, the suggested approach has the best classification performance of all the comparable papers. Furthermore, the suggested approach is found to generate acceptable results with a lesser number of training examples. This paper's significant contributions are given below.

- Deep transfer learning is used to the classification of three types of brain tumors.
- When transfer learned deep CNN features are combined with validated classifier models, performance improves significantly.
- When compared to other approaches, the proposed technique had the highest classification accuracy.
- Even with a low number of training sample, the suggested technique achieves a high level of performance.
- The effects of overfitting with fewer training data on classification performance is investigated and then resolved.

The remaining part of this paper is organized in the following manner. In section 2, we give an overview of the concept of transfer learning, then describe the dataset used in the study and the entire framework for the proposed classification algorithm. Section 3 describes the experiments in detail, presents the evaluation results, and discusses the findings. This paper's conclusion is found in Section 4.

Research Methodology

In this paper, for our classification task we used transfer learning to apply a pre-trained deep network of GoogLeNet.

Transfer learning in inductive setting

Transfer learning is a technique for learning a new set of data using the information obtained by a previously trained model [23]. The goal of transfer learning is to improve learning in D_t using knowledge from D_s and T_s . Given a source domain (D_s) and a learning task (T_s) in the source domain, a target domain (D_t) and the corresponding learning task (T_t), the goal of transfer learning is to improve learning in D_t using knowledge from D_s and T_s . Different parameters for transfer learning are provided based on the kind of task and the nature of the data available at the source and destination domains [7]. When labelled data is available in the source and target domains for a classification job, the transfer learning methodology is known as inductive transfer learning [24]. In this case, the domain is $D = (x_i y_i) I$ where x_i is the feature vector for the i th training sample and y_i denotes the class label for the i th training sample. The following assertions describe the transfer learning environment in relation to our application.

GoogLeNet is a deep network with 22 learnable layers that is defined as a deep network. [25] It has two convolutional layers, two pooling layers, nine inception modules, and a fully connected layer. The architecture of the module is made up of 1×1 , 3×3 , and 5×5 filters [13]. Filters with various kernel sizes are anticipated to catch various data patterns. At the output of each module, the feature maps corresponding to distinct filters are concatenated. Furthermore, 1×1 convolutions are conducted before bigger kernel convolutions.

They are used to reduce the number of dimensions in computation. The ImageNet large scale visual recognition competition (ILSVRC) was won by GoogLeNet in 2014. It was trained using ImageNet's 1.2 million natural images.

Each image in ImageNet corresponded to one of the 1000 classes that had been specified. The source domain is defined by ImageNet training samples, and the source job is a 1000-class classification issue. The classification of brain tumors into three categories is our tasks. Our dataset and target domain are defined by T1-contrast enhanced (CE) MRI images from figshare. [26] The basic of the transfer learning methodology as applied to our work is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Transfer learning setting

Figure 2: GoogleNet Model

Figure 3: Modified GoogleNet

To adapt GoogLeNet to the target domain, we changed the last three layers. In the original GoogLeNet, the fully connected (FC) layer was eliminated. Instead, a new FC layer with a three-size output was added. Following the FC layer, the softmax layer was removed, as was the cross-entropy-based classification layer at the output. Figure 2 depicts the improved deep learning model. The updated GoogLeNet was then fine-tuned by training it on an MRI images from figshare. At the FC layer, the learning parameters for weights and bias were set at a high value of 10. For experiments using MRI data from the figshare dataset, the transfer learned, and fine-tuned deep CNN could then be utilized.

Proposed classification framework

To learn the features of brain MRI images containing tumor, the proposed technique uses a modified and fine-tuned GoogLeNet. (In the rest of this study, the retrieved features using modified GoogLeNet will be referred to as deep CNN features.) For training images, features taken from layers close to the fully connected layer provide effective discriminative representations. The scatter plot of characteristics collected at the FC layer of the transfer learning GoogLeNet is shown in Figure 3. A softmax classifier layer in the transfer learning model can categorize image data from figshare into three tumor classifications. When deep CNN features are added to well-established pattern classifiers, however, performance is projected to increase [27]. The deep CNN features were tested on two sets of classifier models other than the softmax classifier inside deep CNN in the proposed work. The SVM and k-nearest neighbors (KNN) classifiers are used. SVM was chosen for our experiments as a consequence of earlier research that had demonstrated it to be effective in classifying CNN features. When data points are difficult to distinguish using SVM planes, a density estimation-based classifier may be more effective. KNN was considered for our tests as a result of this notion. The overall framework for the proposed classification system is shown in Figure 2,3. Deep CNN features from the training and validation data, as well as training data class labels, are used as inputs to the classifier model. For the validation data, the model predicts and outputs class labels.

Experiments and results

We used MATLAB 2018a to implement the proposed classification model on a PC with 64 GB of RAM.

Dataset and pre-processing

The figshare dataset [26] is freely accessible and is frequently used to evaluate classification and retrieval algorithm [16]. It consists of 3064 brain MRI pictures from 233 individuals who have been diagnosed with one of the three types of brain tumors (meningioma, glioma and pituitary tumors). The images are from a T1-CE MRI scan including coronal, sagittal, and axial views. It includes 1426 MRI images of the brain with glioma (equivalent to 89 patients), 708 images of meningioma (equivalent to 82 patients), and 930 images of pituitary tumors (belonging to 62 patients).

The photos are 512x512 pixels in size and are available as .mat files. GoogLeNet was built from the ground up for RGB colour images, with a 224x224x3 input layer. In terms of intensity values, they were normalized. To scale the intensity values between 0 and 1, a min-max normalization approach was used. They've been resized to 224x224 pixels. Three channels were constructed by reproducing the greyscale values three times since MRI pictures are greyscale pictures.

Feature Selection and Dropping

After collecting 6272 features from Deep feature CNN (updated googlenet). We used NCA (neighborhood component Analysis). Through which we get the weights of each feature and then select top 500 important features out of 6272 features. And dropped all remaining features because they were less important. After that we used these top features for KNN and SVM classifiers. The working of how we do selection features is explained below:

First of all, Pearson's correlation was calculated and the deep features that were highly correlated (80%) to each other are noted. One of the highly correlated features is considered and the remaining are dropped as there is no need for more than one highly correlated feature. After the filtration method, the remaining features are given weights using Neighborhood Component Analysis (NCA) method using MATLAB. The NCA assigned a weight to each feature and sorted the features by their weights. This proposed method resulted in a smaller number of sorted features. The weights of features during applying FCA is shown below.

TUNING ITER	TUNING SUBSET FUN VALUE	LEARNING RATE
1	1.071738e+00	2.000000e-01
2	1.066265e+00	4.000000e-01
3	1.055756e+00	8.000000e-01
4	1.034748e+00	1.600000e+00
5	9.930598e-01	3.200000e+00
6	9.127231e-01	6.400000e+00
7	7.607903e-01	1.280000e+01
8	4.912903e-01	2.560000e+01
9	6.715077e-02	5.120000e+01
10	-4.568261e-01	1.024000e+02
11	-8.517781e-01	2.048000e+02
12	-8.517781e-01	2.048000e+02
13	-8.517781e-01	2.048000e+02
14	-8.517781e-01	2.048000e+02

Figure 4: The weights of features during applying FCA

Classifier settings

The combination of image features and the classifier model determines the performance of an image classification system. There are three different experimental settings for the classifier models utilized in the final step of the proposed brain tumor classification system.

As a stand-alone system, transfer the trained deep CNN model with its softmax classifier

The training set was used to train the modified GoogLeNet (after pre-processing). The network's hyper parameters were heuristically adjusted to facilitate in the convergence of the loss function during training (Fig. 6). Because of the high learning rate and parameter-specific adaptive nature, Adam was picked as the best optimizer. The learning rate for Adam was set to 0.0003. The choice of a high value may prevent the Loss function from converging, resulting in overshoots. In addition, a very low learning rate lengthens the training period. Because of the possibility of overfitting, the number of epochs was limited to ten. Table 1 shows the hyper parameter settings used in our experiment.

Table 1: Experimental parameters

Model	Parameters	Setting (Values)
Transfer Learned Deep Network	initial learning rate	0.0003
	mini-batch size	30
	learning algorithm	Adam
	loss function	cross-entropy
	maximum epochs	10
	learning factor @ fc layer	10
SVM	model sub-type	ECOC hinge
	loss function	One-vs-all
	coding learner	SVM linear
	kernel	L2
	regulation solver	BFGS
KNN	numbers of neighbors	49
	k distance	Euclidean

SVM classifier using Deep CNN features

We retrieved features from the modified Google Net’s pooling layer, which was inserted after the final inception module. SVM was used to classify the features. We employed a multi-class SVM with an ECOC model (error-correcting output code). For multi-class classification, a one-vs-all technique was adopted. Three binary SVM learners, each with a linear kernel, were used. Table 1 lists the SVM’s other parameters.

Deep CNN features with KNN classifier

In a similar manner to the previous setting, features were extracted. The KNN classifier was then used in a classification experiment. KNN’s most important parameters are k , the number of nearest neighbors and the distance measure. According to our cross-validation settings, we picked 49 as the value for k , which is the square root of the number of samples in the training set. A lower k number puts the system at risk of noise and overfitting. A greater value indicates that there will be more calculations. Furthermore, if k is set too large, data imbalances across classes may dominate the findings. The distance measure we employed was Euclidean distance.

Performance evaluation

We measured several performances while using multiple classifiers. When we used stand-alone softmax classifiers by using updated GoogleNet the accuracy was measured 91% shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Accuracy of Transfer learning model

And its loss function also measured which is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Loss function

We attain 100% accuracy by using SVM and 96% accuracy by using KNN before feature selection. Which is shown in Table 2:

Table 2: Model's Accuracy

<i>Algorithms</i>	<i>Accuracy (%)</i>
KNN	95.73
SVM	100

After feature selection the accuracy and loss function was almost same but the complexity of time reduced as the features were less taken which reduce the time to process. We also used another model mobilenet whose architecture is less dense as compared to the googlenet. But it was giving the almost same accuracy. Also giving more features as compared to the googlenet and we already dropped.

Conclusion

This research provides a brain tumor classification method that is both accurate and totally automated, with minimal pre-processing. To extract features, the suggested system used the notion of deep transfer learning. From MRI images of the brain the features were combined with a tried-and-true classifier models that will help you perform better. The best was recorded by the system. When compared to all similar works, classification accuracy is the most important factor. The performance was excellent. We also used NCA to reduce the features and only used important features which helped to save the time. All this indicates that proposed method is suitable for the brain tumors classification using extracted deep features and ML classifiers. As our proposed method's performance is promising, further research work is needed to lessen the model complexity to implement on a real-time medical diagnostics system to save the time using Deep Neural Learning and Machine Learning techniques.

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